

Faris' Representation

(1) Introduction

I am gonna introduce a new way of representing equations and expressions in this article. As functions, logarithms etc are also names of different representations for equations and expressions. Similarly Faris' Representation is also a representation of equations and expressions by MCO separation whose name is Individualer.

(2) Terminology

Faris' Representation

It is a type of representation in which operations and M-Characters are written separately.

General Formula: M-Characters Separator Operations

MCO Separation

MCO Separation (M-Characters Operations Separation) is a method of separating operations and M-Characters in which one writes all M-Characters with single space at left and all operations with single space at right and write them in sequence of given equation or expression and inserts a separator between them.

Example:

Suppose an equation:

$$ab + c/d - e = f$$

There are 6 M-Characters and 11 Operations therefore equation becomes individualer:

$$a\ b\ c\ d\ e\ f\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$$

Individualer

The equations and expressions that are applied MCO Separation to represent them in Faris' Representation are named as Individualer.

Example:

$a\ b\ c\ d\ e\ f\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$ is named as Individualer.

Separator

The small circle is called a separator that separates operations and M-Characters.

Example:

$$a\ b\ c\ d\ e\ f\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$$

The small circle between operations and M-Characters is called a separator.

M-Characters

Coefficients, Constants and Variables are called M-Characters(Math Characters).

Hinters

Hinters are some extra information in individualer.

They are:

1. =, ≠

2. >, ≥, ≤, <

(3)Details

1.Simple Case

Consider an individualer $12\ 3\ 5\ 2\ 1\ 37.5\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$

(A)Representing Equations

There are 3 different situations that can be encountered while representing equations in the simple case.

Case 1 When M-Characters and Operations are known

Individualer:

$12\ 3\ 5\ 2\ 1\ 37.5\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$

Solution:

$$12 \times 3 + 5/2 - 1 = 37.5$$

Case 2 When only Operations are known

Individualer:

$f\ f\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$

Solution:

$a\ b\ c\ d\ e\ f\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$

$$ab + c/d - e = f$$

Case 3 When only M-characters are known

Individualer:

$12\ 3\ 5\ 2\ 1\ 37.5\ \circ\ \sim\ =\ \sim$

Solution:

$$12 \sim 3 \sim 5 \sim 2 \sim 1 = \sim 37.5$$

(B)Representing Expressions

There are 3 different situations that can be encountered while representing expressions in the simple case.

Case 1 When M-Characters and Operations are known

Individualer:

12 3 5 2 1 ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - +

Solution:

$$12 \times 3 + 5/2 - 1$$

Case 2 When only Operations are known

Individualer:

f ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - +

Solution:

a b c d e ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - +

$$ab + c/d - e$$

Case 3 When only M-characters are known

Individualer:

12 3 5 2 1 ◦ ~

Solution:

$$12 \sim 3 \sim 5 \sim 2 \sim 1$$

2. Answer Given Case

Consider an individualer 12 3 5 2 1 37.5 ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - + = +

(A) Representing Equations

There are 3 different situations that can be encountered while representing equations in the answer given case.

Case 1 When M-Characters and Operations are known

Individualer:

12 3 5 2 1 37.5 ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - + = +

Solution:

$$12 \times 3 + 5/2 - 1 = 37.5$$

Case 2 When only Operations are known

Individualer:

37.5 37.5 ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - + = +

Solution:

a b c d e f ◦ + × + + + ÷ + - + = +

$$ab + c/d - e = 37.5$$

Case 3 When only M-characters are known

Individualer:

12 3 5 2 1 37.5 ◦ +=+

Solution:

$$12 \sim 3 \sim 5 \sim 2 \sim 1 = + 37.5$$

(B) Representing Expressions

There are 3 different situations that can be encountered while representing expressions in the answer given case.

Case 1 When M-Characters and Operations are known

Individualer:

$$12\ 3\ 5\ 2\ 1\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ (A\ r=+37.5)$$

Solution:

$$12 \times 3 + 5/2 - 1\ (A\ r=+37.5)$$

(Any alphabet can be used in place of r usually x is used)

Case 2 When only Operations are known

Individualer:

$$a\ b\ c\ d\ e\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ (A\ \sim=+)$$

Solution:

$$ab + c/d - e\ (A\ \sim=+)$$

Case 3 When only M-characters are known

Individualer:

$$12\ 3\ 5\ 2\ 1\ \circ\ \sim\ (A\ r=37.5)$$

Solution:

$$12 \sim 3 \sim 5 \sim 2 \sim 1\ (A\ r=37.5)$$

3.Complex situations

The simple case and answer given case are most simplest and more useful than the other complex situations where any term or operation is missing in either equations or expressions and any term or operation is known in either equations or expressions. Normally you write individualer in the same sequence in which equations and expressions terms are given but you can change the individualer sequence from equations or expressions sequence but these cases are not very useful.

Note:

(1)The bracket is a part of notation of individualer of answer given case of expressions.

(2)One can also add hinters in individualer of either expression or equation like this(whether its a answer given case or simple case):

$$a>b\ c \neq d\ e\ 37.5\ \circ\ +\ \times\ +\ +\ +\ \div\ +\ -\ +\ =\ +$$

(4)Use

This representation can be used for:

(1)Data analysis

(2)Reducing Computer processing power by separating an equation or expression in parts.

(5)Conclusion

In this article I introduced a simple representation and terminology related to it. I explained this representation and wrote it for the simple case and in which answer is provided and told some complex situations where sequence and unknown and known terms are random. It has a new feature of adding hints also. At the end its uses are told.